

Using geomagnetism data to improve geolocation of marine wildlife

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ABSTRACT

This work discusses the potentials of including measurements of geomagnetism in aquatic biotelemetry using archival tags to track marine wildlife with a focus on demersal fish. Despite having many implications for fishery management and wildlife preservation, knowledge derived from studies using electronic tags is rarely included in ocean management actions due to remaining uncertainties. This work poses the question if the consideration of geomagnetism in geolocation could possibly contribute to alleviating these shortcomings. Methodologically, a focus in the literature lies on state-space models and hidden Markov models.

Results indicate that an inclusion of geomagnetic data can improve geolocation when certain factors such as map resolution and geomagnetic variance specification are considered. However, so far, the results are neither unequivocally positive nor widely applicable to different geographic regions. It is concluded that the measuring of geomagnetism should more frequently be employed in studies using archival tags in order to create a better data corpus for future assessment.

KEYWORDS

geolocation, geomagnetism, demersal fish, hidden Markov model, archival tags

1 Introduction and background

The tracking of aquatic animals using electronic archival tags can be relevant to fishery management (e.g. prompting the closure of fisheries when fish stock is low) [1] or the evaluation of spatial management measures like the designation of oceanic protected areas [2]. Archival tags are usually used when fish cannot be tracked “live”, which is often the case because GPS radio frequencies cannot penetrate water. Albeit a common practice at the intersection of marine biology, animal biotelemetry, fisheries ecosystems research, and ecology studies, it still holds many challenges when it comes to questions of precision, consistency, and reliability. This is due to the fact that fish tracks have to be inferred or estimated post-hoc from the recorded environmental variables [3] after retrieval of the archival tag holding this information (see section 2). The resulting errors and uncertainties prevent these studies to be widely incorporated into ocean management measures [4] [5]. This is especially the case for aquatic animals whose migration takes place far below the sea surface and that cannot be traced via more readily available surface-

based environmental factors [6]. This special challenge is why the present work focuses on demersal fish. For example, recent experiments showed that in the case of demersal fish, current state-of-the-art procedures can have an error range too high for small scale applications when considering common measurements [7] [3].

These challenges and their possible solutions all revolve around the single focal point of data. How can better data be obtained, how can data quality and aptitude of tools employed to gather it be verified, how can this data be used most effectively from a methodological perspective and how can these methods be adapted to data from different ecosystems. One possible answer might lie in enriching the amount of considered variables with a novel environmental factor. This work poses the question if geomagnetism can serve as such an additional factor improving geolocation results.

2 Environmental factors commonly considered

The most commonly used environmental properties to infer the geographic position of aquatic fish have been depth measurements, submarine illumination or irradiance and sea surface water temperature (SST) [8] as well as sea bottom temperature (SBT) [3]. These measures are recorded on electronic archival tags attached to the animals which are later retrieved. While maximum diving depth of the animal can be compared to bathymetric maps of the sea floor, irradiance serves the purpose to estimate the apparent length of the day as well as apparent noon to infer probable latitude and longitude respectively. Water temperature can be also compared to reported actual temperatures which are more readily available on the sea surface, less so for SBT.

All of these measures have their limitations: Bathymetry is less useful for fish that do not regularly visit regions close to the sea bottom while, inversely, SST only serves its purpose when the animals can be expected to surface at certain intervals. Irradiance-based estimates of longitude (apparent noon) are more consistent than those of latitude (apparent day length) which loose accuracy with increased depth and prevalence of light-obstructing algae and sessile organisms [8] [9].

3 Method

Methodologically, state-space models (SSM) and – also in the case of demersal fish – especially Hidden Markov Models (HMM) have become widely used in geolocation of tagged marine fish to estimate the likelihood of fish location over the course of an observation period [3]. In such a model, locations are represented in a spatial grid. One of two sub-models predicts the probability of moving from one state, or grid cell, to the next (process model),

while the other predicts the likelihood of an observation, such as finding a fish at a certain place and time (observation model). The two sub-models iteratively update one another at every step and are later backwards filtered or “smoothed” after the tag has been retrieved so that the final state can be accounted for [10].

Although large-scale applications, like the tracking of fish over large migratory paths, have had some success with the state-space models, there remains much room for improvement: Recent double-tagging experiments on demersal fish showed that HMMs can have an error range of 35–50km [7] [3] when considering tidal signal, sea bottom temperature and depth, which is too high for many possible use cases. Thus, in unison with efforts to improve statistical models and the quest to obtain more precise data on environmental factors, novel ideas regarding the *nature* of these factors are a possible route to arrive at a better understanding of migratory paths of demersal fish.

4 Novel approach to include geomagnetism

Even though geomagnetism has been proposed as another environmental factor that could serve to improve the geolocation of aquatic animals already in the early 1990ies [11], it has been largely overlooked and only recently resurfaced. Among 69 scientific papers, a 2021 review of geolocation models for marine fish tracking finds only two studies including this measure [3] Klimley et al. (2017, henceforth referred to as Study A) make an argument to include measurements of geomagnetic field in addition to irradiance and SST while providing evidence that its utility varies by geographic region and time of year. Next to theoretical deliberations, they base their reasoning to some extent on the track of a single buoyant tag drifting across the surface of the northern Atlantic Ocean over a period of 10 months. In doing so, they compare geolocations using magnetic measurements against irradiance-based location and verification based on Doppler-derived positions from the ARGOS satellite network [8].

Nielsen et al. (2020, henceforth Study B) in contrast to Study A, extend the use of geomagnetism measurements to geolocation of demersal fish and estimate locations of simulated random walk trajectories under several different treatments using an HMM. They simulated 1000 random walks in the geographic region of their study in the North Pacific Ocean close to Alaska, where the variables expressed changes in longitude and latitude. They then compared performance of 4 theoretical tag measurement resolutions of geomagnetism (ranging from ± 1000 nT to ± 150 nT), two different map resolutions (100m and 1km), and various methods of geomagnetic variance specification to a depth-only model [6]. For example, the “constant” method (see Fig. 1) assigned all model grid cells with the same value of standard deviation, while others assigned cell variance based on e.g. the standard deviation of values in all adjacent cells (“roughness” method, see Fig. 1). The HMM in Study B was run using the R Package HMMoce and individual code adjustments.

5 Challenges when working with and obtaining geomagnetic data

The earth’s magnetic field ranges from 26,000 nT at the equator to 66,000 nT at the magnetic poles and its intensity consists of the sum of three orthogonal vectors (vertical, north-south, east-west). Using

geomagnetism to infer location will work best in geographic regions where the magnetic field intensity gradient is steep and runs north-south, so that changes in field intensity can be attributed to a change in position most unambiguously. Also, careful calibration when using latitude estimates from magnetic field intensity in areas with significant crustal anomalies, as these can have noticeable effects on the estimate. While the general field intensity varies only slightly between surface level and 2000m below sea level, environmental challenges include magnetic field anomalies caused by geological formations such as volcanic rock as well as solar storms causing temporal fluctuations in magnetic field intensity [8].

Thus, on the methodical and technical side, it has to be considered that magnetic field measurements at surface level might differ from local anomalies detected at the sea bottom. Additionally, the measurement instruments (tags) themselves are rarely equipped to protocol geomagnetism and in Study B, 1 of 5 used tags delivered highly inadequate measurements [6] despite being cost-intensive equipment.

6 Results

Results suggested that the consideration of geomagnetic data can have a positive effect on the geolocation of demersal fishes [8] [6], although Study B showed, that these depended strongly on the appropriate grid resolution and tag measurement resolution. The employed variance specification methods also played a large role in this study, which found that models with specific variance specification methods and including geomagnetic data performed worse than a depth-only model, while others significantly reduced the mean absolute error.

Figure 1: Performance in comparison to depth-only model, Study B [6]

The figure shows performance of the depth-only model compared to various likelihood and tag resolution treatments in Study B. Higher performance is indicated by a lower mean absolute error (MAE) between estimated and simulated locations for 1000 trajectories. V, H, M, and L indicate decreasing levels of tag resolution. In general, higher tag resolution seems to improve performance on the fine-scale map, while the coarse-scale map shows higher variance based on variance specification method [6].

The results suggest the inclusion of geomagnetic data can indeed serve to improve geolocation of demersal fishes in the North Pacific Ocean when combined with depth data in a hidden Markov model framework. But it would have to be ascertained if these results hold true for other geographic regions with different geomagnetic properties. Also, the actual improvement is contingent resolution and accuracy of geomagnetic archival tags as well as the resolution of the magnetic field maps available for the geographic area in question [6].

7 Conclusion and Outlook

In order to ensure the effectiveness of geomagnetism in the geolocation of demersal fishes, more – and more precise data are required in the future. On the one hand, geomagnetic tags need to be adapted to measure the absolute value of magnetic field instead of only its vector components and improvements to calibration procedures are necessary. On the other hand, it would be crucial to provide high-resolution data on the earth's magnetic field at seafloor level to more accurately consider anomalies from volcanic rock or even manmade structures such as shipwrecks or submarine communications cables [6]. Additionally, more case studies must be conducted in geographically distinct locations to be able to compare the utility in different geomagnetic environments. Finally, it is important to note that none of the studies propose that geomagnetism should replace any other environmental factor but should instead be used in addition to established factors.

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